

THE VIRTUAL ROOM AS A TEACHING AND LEARNING TOOL IN BIOLOGY

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Biology teaching, in previous decades, was based almost always on theoretical and expository classes. This way of teaching in High School has been constantly being modified. In addition to being tiring for students, this old model competes with the frequent use of mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets by students. With the advancement of digital information and communication technologies (TDIC), the teaching-learning process has become more dynamic and interactive, in addition to aiming at the collective and collaborative construction of knowledge.

As reported by Alfonso (2019), it is essential that teachers look for alternatives so that their classes keep up with technological evolution. According to Lima et al. (2018), technological strategies in the teaching-learning process with the use of digital environments and tools provide the student's affective approach to the content. As suggested by Neto et al. (2018), one of these strategies is to apply innovative theories with mediation of technologies.

According to Silva (2018, p. 8), Google Classroom “is a tool that creates a virtual classroom, in which the teacher organizes the classes and directs the work, using or not the other Google tools”. This platform is a type of virtual learning environment (VLE) in which the teacher can create a space for each of their classes, adding materials and resources of their own authorship and for disseminating student work.

Considering the difficulties faced by students in Biology content and the restricted time of only two weekly classes lasting fifty minutes each (Minas Gerais, 2016), this work presents a proposal for a hybrid model, which integrates three methodologies: active learning; inverted classroom and blended teaching, all supported and mediated through the use of TDIC, specifically the Google Classroom tool.

The objective of this work is to carry out an integrative teaching-learning proposal using the mentioned VLE. The aim is to develop teaching strategies using technologies and active learning methodologies, making the virtual room a complement to face-to-face moments, in addition to promoting the collective and collaborative construction of knowledge. This experience was applied in the discipline of Biology in a class of 1st year of high school with 34 students, in a state school in the city of Formiga/MG.

Theoretical Reference

Students have difficulties in assimilating and learning the contents covered in Biology in High School, due to the use of teaching methods with traditional resources, since these do not arouse the student's interest, by abstaining from the use of available information and communication technologies in the current context (Silveira; Silva, 2019).

The traditional model collaborates with the lack of interest in the contents dealt with in the classroom, given the lack of proximity to the teacher (Moran, 2015). According to Schiehl and Gasparini (2016), "at school, especially in Elementary and High School, there is still recognition of a physical environment traditionally structured by classrooms, where the training of students takes place". With this, the academic performance of students in the contents of Biology and related disciplines is affected.

For these authors, "each educational institution analyzes with its professionals which scenario or model of hybrid teaching adapts to its structural and functional possibilities". In this context, the educational institution, teachers and school managers must seek alternatives and different methodologies that lead to a more dynamic, integrative and efficient teaching-learning process.

Digital technologies are tools that can assist in the implementation of hybrid education, in addition to being an instrument frequently used by students (Silveira; Silva, 2019). Google Classroom is a platform that is easy to access and use for both teachers and students. With this platform, teaching can be divided into some face-to-face stages and others at a distance.

Google Classroom is free to access, as well as other Google applications, as long as the user only needs to have an account on the site. It is a simple distance learning platform, but at the same time very complete, as it includes several other integrated tools (Veludo, 2018), which allows the creation of classes for the virtual sharing of information and documents (Araújo, 2016).

Silveira (2019) reports that "the teacher, by making use of new technologies, leads the student to build their own knowledge". Gomes, Lima and Fürkotter (2014) mention that "it is essential to use these technologies in favor of education, as they offer new possibilities to users, mainly to produce content, abandoning the passive way of relating to technologies".

The use of Google Classroom provides teachers and students with a modality of face-to-face teaching with extremely relevant distance moments. The TDIC become allied to the teaching-learning process, in addition to developing students' interest in the content.

Google Classroom does not need to be installed locally; according to Souza and Souza (2019), "the platform is already online and hosted, facilitating entry (login) into the platform and the integration of various online tools provided by Google". The insertion of the virtual classroom in High School allows knowledge to be built collectively and collaboratively, in addition to bringing active and constructivist teaching-learning methodologies to High School students.

Methodology

Based on the experiences of the teacher-author in the classroom and on the observation of the students' difficulties in the topics covered in Biology, I tried to set up the virtual room on the Google Classroom platform according to the specifics of the class. Preference was given to posting materials produced by the teacher, such as video lessons, comic books, animations and tests. In cases where it was not possible to produce the content, free and licensed materials were used, so as not to generate expenses for any of the parties involved.

The creation of e-mail accounts for students who did not yet have it and the sending of access codes to the virtual learning environment in Google Classroom were also provided. Training classes for the use of this tool were given to students in the computer lab.

The activities were divided into two parts, which, in turn, have two stages with four activities and a diagnostic evaluation each, totaling ten activities, as detailed in Chart 1. The activities are basically the presentation of classes and the test for verification of learning, which only addresses issues of its specific stage. The diagnostic evaluation has the function of diagnosing the integral content taught in the two stages of the part in question. The tests and assessments have ten multiple-choice questions worth one point each, thus requiring 60% each to pass.

The content of "microorganisms" was used as the object of study, subdivided into four groups: bacteria, fungi, protozoa and viruses, respectively representing each of the four stages of the work, as shown in detail in Table 1.

Table 1: Project structure and its stage divisions

Part	Stage	Activities	Themes
1st Part (written)	1st Stage	Presentation of the first content, exclusively theoretical written test 1	Bacteria
	2nd stage	Presentation of the second theoretical content and AVA written test 2	Fungi
1st diagnostic evaluation (written)			
2nd Part (online)	3rd Stage	Presentation of the third theoretical content and AVA Online test at AVA 1	Protozoa
	4th Stage	Exhibition of the fourth content exclusively on AVA Online test in AVA 2	Virus

2nd diagnostic evaluation (Online)

The division of work into two parts aims to verify and compare the performance of students against the use of traditional teaching methodology with the methodology used in the virtual learning environment. Thus, with the results of each part, it is possible to analyze the efficiency of one or another teaching-learning methodology.

The first part is exclusively “written”, that is, in the traditional way of teaching, with lectures and the use of blackboard, chalk, textbook and notebook. The first content was taught in this way, followed by its respective test, also applied on paper.

In the second stage, the transition process began, in which the presentation of the content took place with alternating theoretical presentations and the use of the AVA Google Classroom in the school's computer lab. The test for this step was written and printed. After the end of the second test, the first diagnostic evaluation was performed, also applied in printed form. The activity notes were delivered after a week for the teacher to make the necessary corrections.

The second part consists of online activities . The exposition of the third content, in the third stage, was represented by the continuation of the transition of the methodology, so that the content was also explained by alternating the traditional and written forms in the classroom, with the online method using the VLE. The test of this stage was carried out exclusively online at AVA, in order to deepen the use of the methodology. This test was produced using Google Forms, which provides instant feedback to the student, with receipt of the grade immediately upon completion.

The exhibition of the fourth content was carried out exclusively in the AVA, using materials authored by the teacher. Classes were held in the school's computer lab. With its completion, the application of the test was also carried out in the AVA. Then, the 2nd diagnostic evaluation was also applied in its online form .

Results

Considering that the passing grade is 6.0, it is clear that the overall average of the class was below expectations, ranging between 4.12 and 4.88 throughout the first part, which was carried out in the traditional teaching model, including the lecture exposure models, the two tests and the assessment.

The graph in Figure 1 shows that, from the moment the AVA Google Classroom started to be adopted in classes, the general average jumps from 4.88 in evaluation 1 to 6.35 in the first online test . This ascent goes until the end of the second part, with an average of 7.06 in evaluation 2.

Figure 1: Overall average of students' Biology grades

A positive point pointed out by students is the possibility of receiving grades immediately, not having to wait for the teacher to make corrections. The feedback of the activities is sent immediately after sending the activity by the student, causing him to seek study content that had more difficulty and mistakes.

When the number of students with grades below or above the expected average is analyzed (60%), it is clearly observed that there is a drop in the number of students with grades below the average, as the AVA Google Classroom methodology is adopted, as shown in Figure 2.

In the second written test, there was an increase of four students with grades below the average. This fact may be related to the beginning of the adoption of the new methodology, in which the exposure of classes was carried out alternating between classroom and distance education. From this test, over time, the students gained familiarity with the methodology, causing the number of low averages to suffer the first drop, to 23 students.

The first online test brought very positive results, considering that 76.5% of students had above average grades. In the second online test, this percentage showed a new increase, reaching 91% of students with above-average grades.

When comparing the scores of the two diagnostic evaluations, the result is also very positive. In the first assessment, only 32% of students had above-average grades; in the second, this percentage rose to 88%. These results demonstrate the relevance of using the virtual room in the class.

Figure 2: Total students below/above 60% in Biology

At the end of the development of activities, students were asked about the use of the AVA Google Classroom during classes and Biology assessments. For 89% of them, the use of this methodology was positive and productive; they considered it important that teachers from other disciplines also implement this tool in their classes.

Conclusions

The virtual room implemented with Google Classroom made it possible for students and professors to meet in a virtual learning environment, even though High School is practiced in the face-to-face mode. The tool helped those involved both in exposing the contents and in didactic assessments. In this environment, it was possible to post different types of materials produced by the teacher, in addition to encouraging students to produce extra materials. It is observed that the grades and academic performance of the class had considerable improvements.

As the students' suggestions point out, it is necessary that teachers from other disciplines and grades seek to develop teaching-learning methodologies similar to this one, with the help and mediation of digital information and communication technologies. The creation and maintenance of a virtual room provides facilities for the teacher, making them the author of their materials, with the possibility of sharing them with other colleagues, in order to obtain specific teaching materials for the reality of the class in which they work.

The results were quite significant in terms of academic performance, students' interest and curiosity in Biology, which were reawakened by this practice.

References

ALFONSO, Carolina Moreira. Innovative practices in science and biology teaching: diversity in adversity. *Education and Teaching Practice Magazine* , No. 2, 2019.

ARAÚJO, Helenice Maria Costa et al. The use of the tools in the Google Classroom application in teaching Mathematics. Monography. Catalan, 2016.

GOMES, Joyce Galdino; LIMA, Claudia Maria de; FÜRKOTTER, Monica. Potentialities of using Facebook from a media-education perspective. National Congress on Teacher Training. São Paulo State University (Unesp). *Annals ...* p. 9,957-9,969. 2014.

LIMA, Rebeka Rayane Araujo de et al. The use of innovative methodologies in Science classes: how to explore them in teaching Virology. V Conedu – National Congress of Education. *Annals... v. 1*, 2018.

MINAS GERAIS. State Department of Education. SEE Resolution No. 2842/16. High School in Minas Gerais state public schools. Belo Horizonte, January 18, 2016. Available at: <http://www2.educacao.mg.gov.br/images/documentos/2842-16-r.pdf>. Accessed on: 31 Aug. 2019.

MORAN, José. Hybrid education: a key concept for education today. In: BACICH, L.; TANZI NETO, A.; TREVISANI, FM (Orgs.). *Hybrid teaching: personalization and technology in education*. Porto Alegre: I think, 2015.

GRANDSON, Agemiro Remigio; PEREIRA, Elba Leandro Nobrega; OLIVEIRA, Jorge Miguel Lima. Google Classroom as a mediator in the teaching-learning process. V Conedu – National Congress of Education. *Annals... v. 1*, 2018.

SCHIEHL, Edson Pedro; GASPARINI, Isabela. Google Classroom contributions to hybrid teaching. *Note* , v. 14, No. 2, 2016.

SILVA, Edivan Claudino Soares. Google Classroom as a learning interface in higher education. International Symposium on Education and Communication – Simeduc, nº 9. *Anais...* 2018.

SILVEIRA, Jader Luís da. Use of Facebook as an educational tool for teaching Biology in High School. *P@rtes* , São Paulo, vol. 1, No. 0, p. 1, 2019.

SILVEIRA, Jader Luís; SILVA, Jefferson Rodrigues da. Biology teaching with authoring tools on the internet. *Public Education* , v. 19, No. 20, September 10, 2019. Available at: <https://educacaopublica.cecierj.edu.br/artigos/19/20/docencia-em-biologia-com-as-ferramentas-de-autoria-na-Internet>. Accessed on: 11 Sept. 2019.

SOUZA, Affonso; SOUZA, Flavia. Use of the Google Classroom platform as a tool to support the teaching-learning process: Application report in high school. Available at: <https://repositorio.ufpb.br/jspui/bitstream/123456789/3315/1/ACSS30112016.pdf>. Accessed on: 11 Sept. 2019.

VELVET, Marco Antonio Manzan. Google Classroom: applied to elementary school students from a private school in Uberaba/MG. Thesis (Master's degree). Uberaba, 2018.